

A STUDY ON THE EFFICIENCY OF POP-UP ADS IN FOOD DELIVERY APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

Digital communication with customers is the new trend in today's world. The impact of pop-up advertisements plays a major role in the company's overall sales, thereby boosting overall profitability. Previous research has an implication on pop-up ads and its positive impact on consumer purchasing behavior. However, there are limited studies as per Stimuli Reaction Theory (SR theory), this study implies SR theory and its impact on the perception of consumers. Previous researches have shown that how ads impact the consumer purchasing behaviour. However, not much study has been done in the area where SR model is used to show how the consumers perceive the pop-up ads and how they react accordingly based on the situation. This paper tries to implicate SR model and try to understand how the POP-UP ads are perceived by the customers. A total of 233 respondents were considered for the study, concluding that based on the timing of the pop-up ads there are moderate chances that the consumer will purchase the order. The study also concludes that the content and the relationship with the customer has to be maintained to increase the order volume. The proposed model can be used for future studies to get clear insight of the stimuli. There is scope for future research to be conducted on longitudinal study to understand whether the consumer will reassess the facilities and benefits after the customer has experienced the impact of pop-up ads.

Keywords: Digital Communication, Pop-up Advertisements, Food delivery Apps, Customer Satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

The Rationale for the Study and Motivation

The computing and communication sectors have undergone a major revolution, thanks to the Internet. This unmatched skill integration was made possible by the simultaneous invention of the telegraph, telephone, radio, and computer. The Internet serves as a platform for cooperation and communication between individuals and their computers, regardless of location, as well as a global broadcasting capacity. One of the best examples of the advantages of long-term commitment and investment in information infrastructure research and development is the Internet.

The National (or Global or Galactic) Information Infrastructure, as it is popularly known, was initially prototyped by the Internet, which is now a widely utilized information infrastructure. It also has a lengthy and complex past that spans several aspects, including technological, organizational, and social. The effect of online technologies goes beyond the technical spheres of computer communications to the rest of society as we move toward increasing employment of them for electronic commerce, data collecting,

and community activities. The channel via which a marketing message is conveyed to the audience is the primary difference between digital and traditional marketing. Digital marketing focuses on digital platforms like social media and websites whereas traditional marketing relies on print media like magazines and newspapers.

As we are in the 21st century the world is becoming more digital. Traditional marketing techniques are not so in picture nowadays. Though they are in practice still it does not reach more people. The growth and increase of usage of internet is a boon for the marketers.

The majority of marketers are now utilizing the internet revolution to make their products available to people all over the world, according to Yaveroglu and Donthu's 2008 analysis. Digital marketing is a term that was first used in the 1990s. The digital era burst with the creation of the internet and the Web 1.0 platform.

Although the Web 1.0 platform allowed users to access and exchange information, it did not allow them to disseminate it across a website. At the time, marketers from all over the world were still wary of the internet platform. Due to the fact that the internet had not yet gained widespread use, they were unsure if their plans would succeed [1].

Modern digital business consists of a huge network of channels into which marketers only need to connect their brands; yet, online advertising is far more difficult than just using the channels.

To realise the full potential of digital marketing, marketers must do a thorough analysis of today's vast and complicated cross-channel world in order to pinpoint strategies that generate effect through engagement marketing. By interacting with consumers online, we may raise brand recognition, become recognised as an industry thought leader, and put our business in front of customers' minds when they're ready to make a purchase.

By utilizing an omni channel digital marketing approach, marketers may provide new channels for client engagement while also gaining insightful information about the behavior of their target audience. Businesses should genuinely anticipate an increase in client retention.

Applications for e-commerce are used across a range of sectors, including production, wholesale, and retail. People are already accustomed to purchasing on their phones. It's simply handier than waiting for a computer. Our phones are always within reach, whereas a laptop or desktop computer it isn't always the case. Consumers purchase from a variety of sources. People can shop on the bus, train, or Uber thanks to mobile commerce. They purchase online during their lunch break or while walking down the street with a cup of coffee. It's simply too simple.

Mobile app development is the ideal option for a business e-Commerce site to get a share of the pie as mobile sales continue to rise in the future years. Food delivery applications come under the E-commerce Industry.

POP up Advertisements

In the latest times, the use of smartphone and internet have increased which is a major advantage for marketers to target the customer. A pop-up notification is a message that gets displayed on the screen by the app generally advertisements or promotions. It is one of the main effective and efficient way of targeting and communicating with the customers nowadays.

It's difficult to get customers to engage and re-engage with mobile apps. Push Ads are one method of reaching online users. Pop up Ads are a quick and easy way to reach out to your audience.

Many mobile apps have a large number of potential consumers who have downloaded but never used them. Pop up Ads are a great approach to get inactive users to become active. The company sends people meaningful reminders, personalized discounts, and breaking news via pop-up notification messages. The organization is considerably more likely to retain people for the long run if the mobile Ads can demonstrate direct personal value. It helps to keep in touch with the customer in a non-intrusive manner.

Since the company may notify customers or create a sense of urgency, timely marketing messages are the best approach to enhance conversion rates. People add products to their shopping carts but abandon the app before finishing their transaction or purchase [2]. To address this issue and reclaim lost customers, the company can employ pop-up ads to deliver reminders to users who exit the application without making a purchase while an item is still in their cart. In comparison to traditional mobile advertising, the organization may enhance its re-targeting click-through rate by using pop-up alerts.

The company can use pop up Ad's to drive immediate purchasing. Send useful messages to your customers and educate them about special discounts or limited-time offers in the app. Push Ads can also enable one-tap purchase in addition to this information.

Mobile applications can request permission to access a user's location. If customers agree, the company will be able to customize the customer experience by sending location-specific push alerts. A mobile application can provide offers to users in a specified time zone who are located in that location. Users might be targeted based on their country, state, or city.

Another important advantage of pop-up Ad's is that they assist in the tracking of user behavior. Complex metrics are available for pop up Ad's, including delivery receipts, open rates, open times, and engagement. You can receive useful insights into user behavior with pop up Ad's, such the likelihood that a message will be opened, such as engagement times and click-through rates [3]. The company may launch campaigns that better interact with users based on user behavior data.

Pop up notification providers can include deep links in push messages that take users to specific locations within your app. Deep links are a guaranteed way to engage users with your app, and when combined with a strong call to action, users are more likely to take the desired action.

Food delivery applications

The Indian service industries, such as banking, food, transportation, business services, and insurance, provide a wide range of services in this digitalized era. Food delivery businesses have become increasingly digitized in recent years. With the use of these online services, users will be able to choose from a larger number of restaurants at the touch of a smartphone [4].

Numerous formats exist for food delivery services. From fully integrated models that keep everything in-house to systems that work with restaurants and drivers, they cover the gamut.

SR Theory

According to the Stimuli Reaction Theory (SRT), which is a psychological theory, behavior develops as a result of how the stimulus and reaction interact [5]. The idea is that a person receives a stimulus, reacts to it, and then exhibits "behavior" (the focus of psychology as a discipline of study). To put it another way, conduct can't exist without some kind of stimulation, at least from this perspective [6].

Fig 1.1: Stimulus Response Theory

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

To better understand how viewers tend to consider commercials as bothersome and choose to avoid them, this article examines the forced viewing of "pop-up ads" on the Internet. Perceived intrusiveness has been considered as the basic mechanism through which the process operates. As antecedents of intrusiveness that influence perceptions of advertisements as interruptions, it was discovered that the correspondence between the content of the advertising and the present task and the degree of cognition at the moment the ad shows up. It was discovered that the reasons of the outcomes of intrusiveness were irritation and ad avoidance. The research provides insight into how consumers respond to forced exposure in interactive settings and highlights implications for advertisers hoping to increase the efficiency of online advertising [3].

Prior research has mostly examined consumer attitudes toward online services/retailing in general and a few researchers have talked about the experiences that customers have had with online food delivery (OFD) businesses. The aim of this study is to investigate the structural relationship between consumer attitude and behavioral intention towards OFD services, convenience motivation, post-usage usefulness, hedonic motivation, price-saving orientation, time-saving orientation, prior online purchase experience, and consumer orientation [8].

According to the trend of ordering food through mobile phones, people are becoming famous because of the busy lives that people are currently leading in society. In the last few years, ordering food has become much more common than cooking food at home and it has become much easier to order food to our homes these days with the aid of technology. With the aid of a questionnaire, the authors were able to know that those food ordering apps are familiar to the majority of people who filled out the survey [14].

Research was conducted to see if the food and service is satisfactory when compared to a traditional dining experience. Mr. Bhat helps us understand the consumer equilibrium with this research paper. It also helped in analysing customer behaviour and satisfaction level [13]. The study attempts to determine the effects of mobile phone marketing from meal delivery applications on the IT employees at Infopark, Kochi (Kerala). The IT professionals at Infopark, Cochin, based their quantitative study on how often people buy meals through mobile applications like Swiggy and Zomato, among others. 250 Information Technology (IT) professionals that work in Quantitative study was conducted on 410 IT companies. These IT professionals were the subjects of a survey employing a particular questionnaire [12].

This research perceived intrusiveness, ad annoyance, and ad avoidance are affected by the timing of pop-up commercial presentation. An experiment was made with the intention of simulating an online environment (complete with homepage major content and a pop-up advertisement) and tweaking the timing of the pop-up advertisement's appearance. Before being assigned to a specific target browsing activity in which their ad-surfing behaviours were monitored, participants were invited to take part in two tests. An eye-tracking tool was utilised to get accurate psychological data that is both objective and exact in order to measure their cognitive aversion to advertising [15].

The stimulus response model of consumer behaviour is effective for understanding individual consumer buying behaviour in the context of individual customers making consumer product purchases. An expanded stimulus-response model of behavioural processes in consumer decision making incorporates the effect and linkages of buyer psychology, a variety of buyer attributes, and the impact of the buyer choice process on consumer decision making. There has been proposed an aggregate level framework of consumer decision-making behavioural processes, which may enable a more thorough investigation of the micro level components and links influencing consumer decision-making behaviour [7].

Mass consumer marketplaces (consumer behaviour) and industrial markets (industrial behaviour) have long been used as research vantage points for studying buyer behaviour (organisational buyer behaviour). This convergence is depicted by a "composite" buyer behaviour model, which is assumed to be equally relevant to every kind of purchasing decisions. The main goal is to present a compact model that encompasses both the key aspects and the underlying process involved in purchasing decisions. The model is made up of eight components or variables, each of which is defined and detailed in some detail, as well as the underlying process model that connects them. While the model is thought to capture the essence of consumer behaviour, its implementation, like other parts of

marketing, is considered as "context specific," necessitating the use of judgement and expertise by those who desire to operationalize it [9].

METHODOLOGY

The methods or the techniques which has been followed for sampling is Non probability convenient & Judgmental sampling technique where the questions are created and setup and it has been distributed among various peoples of different age groups such as friends, family members, neighbors and the data or the information which has been obtained can be used for basic analysis and interpretation purposes.

In this study, 233 people of different ages were given questionnaires, and 233 people responded. As a result, the study's findings are solely dependent on the opinions of those 233 respondents. Data was collected using a self-administered, standardized questionnaire. The questions were aimed to understand how individuals react to the Pop-Up Ad's they get from the food delivery applications and five-item variable scales were used. This includes Attitude, Subjective Norms, Perceived Behavioral Control, Type of notification and the Food delivery application. Based on this, variable a standardized questionnaire was prepared and distributed to people among different age groups and responses were gathered. The aspects that affect respondents' decisions while making purchases after receiving POP-UP notifications were rated by the respondents. Respondents were asked to rank the service characteristics that, in their opinion, affect their choice to make a purchase using a meal delivery application.

Secondary data here was gathered from a variety of sources, including articles, research papers, and literature, as well as other websites and pages that contained information and specifics about my topic. The acquired data was evaluated using Microsoft Excel, which produces graphs and percentages as output. All items were tested for dependability (statistics) in this study. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as charts and graphs in this study. In addition, testing hypotheses is done using regression analysis.

FINDINGS

The stimulus response hypothesis is the foundation of this study. Here, the stimulus is a pop-up advertisement, and the reaction to it is how the person responds to it. The notion that behavior develops as a result of the interaction between stimulus and reaction is known in psychology as the stimulus response theory. Particularly, it is believed that a stimulus is provided to a person, who then reacts to it to produce "behavior" (the topic of psychology as a discipline of study). In other words, at least from this viewpoint, conduct cannot occur without some kind of stimulation.

Based on the time and how the respondents perceive the pop-up ad they have answered it. It can be seen that an individual will open the food delivery application seeing the PROMOPOP-UP notification and will make a purchase has a moderate relationship with the variable. Findings are though the Food delivery applications try to attract the

customers through popups the individuals who read it do not perceive it in the same way at all times. So the response may vary at times from individual to individuals.

It is useful to be in touch with the customer but we should not burden her with many ads and spam her. There should be a limitation when and how to send the pop up notification. The food delivery applications cannot always send the Ad's and burden the customer. They should look onto to that they maintain a healthy relationship with the customer by timely conveying the message and not burdening the customer. They should try to attract non active customers with specifically targeted ads to increase the app traffic which will be useful to them increasing the customer base.

CONCLUSION

In the latest times the use of smartphones and internet have increased which is a major advantage for marketers to target the customer. A pop-up notification is a message that gets displayed on the screen by the app generally advertisements or promotions. It is one of the main effective and efficient ways of targeting and communicating with customers nowadays. Another important advantage of pop-up ads is that they assist in the tracking of user behavior. Complex metrics are available for pop-up ads, including delivery receipts, open rates, open times, and engagement. You can receive useful insights into user behavior with pop-up ads, such as interaction times and click-through. For the future studies it was suggested that multiple theories can be used to explain variables and behaviors, and provided they should be adapted to the industry. Creating a framework that combines these models in order to distinguish more details in variables and behaviors may result in a true improvement.

The current research was carried out in the Food delivery industry. Our proposed model could be used in the future for more studies. Longitudinal study should be done in the future since consumers will reassess the facilities and benefits once they have experienced it once.

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